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Ccl2 functions in endoderm specification of stem cells.

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The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm, mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We describe a requirement for *CCL2* in germ layer lineage choice from pluripotent stem cells in *Homo sapiens*. A chemokine has endogenous functions in development prior to acquisition of the fetal or adult immune system.

Citations

1. Qian, B.Z., Li, J., Zhang, H., Kitamura, T., Zhang, J., Campion, L.R., Kaiser, E.A., Snyder, L.A. and Pollard, J.W., 2011. CCL2 recruits inflammatory monocytes to facilitate breast-tumour metastasis. *Nature*, 475(7355), pp.222-225.